

The Effect of Green Kitchen Practices on Restaurant Choice Intentions¹

Yeşil Mutfak Uygulamalarının Restoran Seçim Niyetine Etkisi

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Abstract

This study focuses on consumers' attitudes and behavioral intentions when choosing environmentally friendly restaurants with green kitchen practices (GKP). This is an under-researched area despite the growing green movement. This framework aims to obtain information about consumers' attitudes and understand whether attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control impact individuals' intention to choose a restaurant. In this context, the studies in the literature were investigated, and a research model was proposed. Face-to-face and online survey methods were applied to measure the perceptions of the variables in the research model. The research sample consists of 428 participants residing in Istanbul, Izmir and Bursa, where GKP are intense. The data obtained from the research were analyzed using structural equation modeling. As a result of the analysis, the model proposed in the study was accepted, and the proposed hypotheses were supported. As a result of the research, in line with the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), it was found that attitude towards behavior (ATB), subjective norm (SN), and perceived behavioral control (PBC) have statistically significant and positive effects on restaurant choice intention. In line with this result, the outputs reached will contribute to academia and the sector.

Keywords: Green Restaurant, Green Kitchen Practices, Sustainability, Green Awareness, Theory of Planned Behaviour.

JEL Codes: L83,Q01,Q56,D12

Özet

Bu çalışma, çevre dostu restoranları seçerken tüketicilerin tutumları ve davranışsal niyetlerine odaklanmaktadır. Yeşil mutfak uygulamaları olan restoranlar konusundaki bu yaklaşım, büyüyen yeşil hareketine rağmen az araştırılmış bir alandır. Bu çalışma, tüketicilerin tutumları hakkında bilgi edinmeyi ve tutumların, öznel normların ve algılanan davranışsal kontrolün bireylerin restoran seçme niyeti üzerindeki etkilerini anlamayı amaçlamaktadır. Bu bağlamda, literatürdeki çalışmalar incelenmiş ve bir araştırma modeli önerilmiştir. Araştırma modelindeki değişkenlerin algılarını ölçmek için yüz yüze ve çevrimiçi anket yöntemleri uygulanmıştır. Araştırmanın örnekleme, yeşil mutfak uygulamalarının yoğun olduğu İstanbul, İzmir ve Bursa'da ikamet eden 428 katılımcıdan oluşmaktadır. Araştırmadan elde edilen veriler, yapısal eşitlik modellemesi kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir. Analiz sonucunda çalışmada önerilen model kabul edilmiş ve önerilen hipotezler desteklenmiştir. Araştırma sonucunda, Planlanmış Davranış Teorisi doğrultusunda, davranışa yönelik tutum, öznel norm ve algılanan davranışsal kontrolün, restoran seçme niyeti üzerinde istatistiksel olarak anlamlı ve olumlu etkilerinin olduğu bulunmuştur. Bu sonuç doğrultusunda, elde edilen bulgular akademiye ve sektöre katkı sağlayacaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yeşil Restoran, Yeşil Mutfak Uygulamaları, Sürdürülebilirlik, Yeşil Farkındalık, Planlanmış Davranış Teorisi.

JEL Kodları: L83,Q01,Q56,D12

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1. Introduction

With the environmental problems emerging with industrialization, many businesses must develop practices to minimize environmental damage and adopt strategic methods. Sustainable development tools and the concept of sustainability, set by the United Nations in 2016 to protect the world and ensure everyone lives in prosperity, are frequently discussed. With the concept of sustainability, environmental awareness is gaining importance at the social level. Individuals in society support this awareness by using environmentally friendly products. Businesses that operate in the field of food and beverage and have recently attracted the attention of conscious consumers are characterized as green restaurants (Yong, Chua, Fakfare, & Han, 2024). Restaurants with GKP use local and organic products and pioneer practices such as energy and water efficiency, waste management and environmentally friendly packaging. In this context, green restaurants in the literature mean 'minimizing the environmental damage of food service businesses' (Kilicraz, 2023).

In the literature, many studies have emphasized how important sustainability is in restaurant preferences with the increasing sensitivity of consumers to the environment (Apak & Gürbüz, 2022). As an indicator of sustainability in food and beverage establishments, the effect of green kitchen practices on individuals' restaurant preference intention is increasing (Eren, Uslu, & Aydın, 2023). Doszhanov and Ahmad (2015) found that environmentally conscious or green practices increasingly influence consumer behavior. They pay attention to this when choosing the restaurants where they want to eat. Aishwarya, Divya, Abinaya, and Rajakrishan (2023) reported in their research that consumers are willing and aware of GKP and that consumers who go green are thus considering sustainable development. The concept of "sustainable development" was defined for the first time in the Brundtland Report prepared by the World Commission on Environment and Development in 1987 as "development that meets the needs of today while taking into account the needs of future generations" (Tomislav, 2018).

Although some studies have addressed consumers' sensitivity to green kitchen practices, there needs to be a more in-depth analysis of whether GKP affects attitudes, subjective norms, and PBC on restaurant preference intention. There is limited research on whether individuals' adequate knowledge and awareness levels, especially about Green kitchen practices, impact their preference intentions. While some studies have reported that individuals are willing to pay more to buy green, studies on economic sustainability are limited. Some studies focus on short-term intentions and behaviors of individuals regarding environmentally friendly restaurant preferences. This field does not examine the effects of

long-term preference intentions on sustainability.

It is thought that the empirical application of the study will contribute to raising awareness about the impact of businesses' green kitchen practices on consumers' behavioral intentions. In addition, the findings and suggestions to be presented will be able to guide researchers, managers and policy makers working on the subject. The purpose of this study is to reveal consumers' intention to choose restaurants with GKP and consumers' intention to choose green restaurants within the scope of the Ajzen model, the TPB. For this purpose, the quantitative research method was utilized. As a result of the research, it is understood that consumer intention to prefer restaurants with environmentally friendly green practices is positive.

2. Conceptual Framework

Green Restaurant and Practices

Climate change is considered a global problem, a multidimensional crisis that causes environmental, economic, and social effects. In order to reduce these effects, countries are trying to take new measures with a new agreement after the Kyoto Protocol. In combating climate change, the Paris Agreement has established a framework to determine implementation procedures regarding national contributions, mitigation, adaptation, loss/damage, financing, technology development and transfer, capacity building, transparency, and situation assessment (mfa.gov.tr). While many sectors are taking precautions against carbon emissions, the food and beverage sector must also take its share of responsibility for environmental destruction. One of the areas where measures need to be taken within the industry is food waste. Ncube et al. (2021) found that food and beverage activities are one of the areas where waste generation problems are most common.

On average, 10 million people die of hunger in the world every year, while 1.3 billion tons of food goes to waste. Considering that 1.5 tons of bread goes to waste every day in Turkey, it becomes clearer how serious the waste is (tarimtv.gov.tr). Not only domestic consumers are responsible for this waste, but also the food and beverage sector. Therefore, to reduce the amount of waste in the food and beverage sector, transform waste, ensure energy efficiency and provide a conscious consumption approach, Turkey and Boğaziçi University - World Wildlife Fund (WWF) initiated the "Green Generation Restaurant Movement" (Akay, 2022). Many practices of restaurants, from waste management to energy use, from sustainable furniture to building materials, from water use to organic food use, are included in this movement. Davies and Konisky (2000) argue that the environmental impact of the food and beverage service industry takes three different forms. These are;

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- Direct Impacts (solid waste consumption, gas absorption, energy consumption, food safety, refrigerants, water emissions)
- Upper Environmental Impacts (pesticides, air pollution)
- Sub-Environmental Impacts (use of bags, use of disposable plates)

From this point of view, green restaurants are food and beverage businesses that serve with environmentally friendly practices and have a structure focused on sustainability principles (Kurnaz & Özdoğan, 2018). These restaurants must be ecologically sensitive regarding using local and organic products, energy efficiency, recycling, and waste reduction. They should also strive to reduce their carbon footprint, conserve natural resources, and save water. While countries in different parts of the world have successful examples of green kitchen practices, various researchers have examined these businesses.

Dutta, Umashankar, Choi, and Parsa (2008), in their study on consumers' orientation towards restaurants with green practices in India and the United States, investigated the attitudes and behavioral intentions of individuals and concluded that environmentally friendly individuals prefer restaurants with green practices, while health-conscious individuals in the USA prefer restaurants with organic, local and healthy food and beverages and green practices. In another study conducted in the USA, it was reported that health issues are among the problems that health-conscious customers consider when choosing a green restaurant (Dewald, Bruin, & Jang, 2013).

Schubert, Kandampully, Solnet and Kralj (2010) investigated the attitudes of consumers towards restaurants with GKP in the USA and reported that customers who care about green prefer restaurants with environmentally friendly and green practices, even if the cost of eating and drinking is high. Dewald et al. (2013) investigated the attitudes of US consumers towards green restaurants. They found that 70% of the participants were willing to pay more for green foods accepted as environmentally friendly products. Sarmiento and El Hanandeh (2018) conducted a study in Australia to determine consumers' perceptions of environmentally sustainable restaurants. They found that customers prefer green restaurants and are willing to pay a high cost to receive green services.

Aishwarya et al. (2023) stated that factors such as climate change, waste management problems, water scarcity, decrease in biodiversity and stress, along with the increase in carbon in the atmosphere that emerged after the 2000s, gradually affect our lives, analyzed the attitudes of consumers towards the adoption of GKP in their study and found that consumers who are aware of climate changes tend towards Green Kitchen Practices.

Oğuz and Sever (2023) investigated customers' en-

vironmental attitudes, behaviors, and sensitivities with high ecological awareness of their intention to choose a green kitchen. They concluded that they positively affect consumers' preference for green businesses.

These studies highlight several essential findings on consumers' attitudes, behaviour, satisfaction, loyalty and willingness to pay. Research in the literature reveals how much consumers value environmentally friendly restaurant practices. In this context, studies show that individuals are more likely to prefer businesses that prioritize green initiatives and use environmentally safe products. Furthermore, research shows that green practices can positively influence customer reviews and loyalty.

In their study, Eren et al. (2023) tested the hypotheses they formed by proposing a model regarding customers' intention to revisit green image and service quality. As a result of the research, they reported that the service quality perceived by customers can significantly influence the perceived green image of a restaurant by its customers. In this study, it is foreseen that more research is needed using the determinants of intentions in the TPB developed by Ajzen (1991), namely attitude towards behavior (ATP), SN and perceived behavioral control, to determine and understand the effect of GKP on restaurant choice intention, which has recently become an increasingly important research topic.

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

Consumer decision-making processes have been the subject of many studies. The theory of planned behavior is an alternative approach to understanding the consumer decision-making process. PDT was developed by Ajzen (1991) to predict and explain consumer behavior. This theory examines not only the will control of individuals but also the will control outside of them while explaining their behavior. Personal intention provides the most obvious prediction of the behavior to be performed (Ajzen, 1991).

ATB is the individual's experiences due to the actions they have performed. In other words, it is the positive or negative evaluation of behavior (Ajzen, 1991). Many studies have reported that individuals' attitudes and behaviors towards businesses with environmentally friendly practices are positive (Dutta et al., 2008; Eren et al., 2023; Schubert et al., 2010; Han & Kim, 2010). Some studies have reported that consumers are ready to pay high costs for green services (Dewald et al., 2013; Sarmiento & El Hanandeh, 2018). In this context, the intention to choose a restaurant with GKP will be higher if the individual has a positive attitude towards environmentally friendly businesses. Therefore, the following hypothesis was developed to determine the attitude of environmentally friendly individuals to support or not sup-

port GKP when choosing a restaurant.

H1: Individuals' attitudes towards GKP positively affect restaurant choice intention.

The SN refers to the social compulsion for an individual to act. In other words, it relates to the expectation or subjective probability that the individual or group (family, spouse, friend, colleague, doctor, or manager) that the individual refers to will approve or disapprove of the behavior. Many studies argue that perceived social influence can replace the SN in the context of pressures from society rather than from valued individuals (Bissonnette & Contento, 2001). A study conducted in Taiwan reported that social influence did not have a positive effect on behavioral intention (BI) (Chou, Chen, & Wang, 2012). On the contrary, Han and Kim (2010), as a result of their research on the formation of customers' intention to revisit a hotel with green practices, revealed that SN has an effect. In other words, it is associated with social pressure for the individual to revisit the hotel. Therefore, the following hypothesis was developed to determine whether social pressure exists to realize the intention to support green kitchen practices.

H2: Individuals' subjective norms about supporting green cuisine practices positively affect restaurant choice intention.

PBC is a vital part of the TPB. PBC is assumed to moderate the effect of attitude and SN on intention, while actual behavioral control is considered to moderate the impact of intention on action (Ajzen, 2020). To the extent that individuals have control over the performance of the behavior, they are expected to be able to act in line with their intentions. When there is insufficient information about actual behavioral control, PBC can help predict behavior in the belief that it accurately reflects actual control.

Some research has shown that the adoption of green practices in restaurants can have a positive impact on customer evaluation and loyalty. For example, in a study conducted in Taiwan that combines the TPB with the theory of innovation adoption, attitude and PBC were found to positively affect the adoption of green practices (Chou et al., 2012). On the contrary, Kargiglioğlu (2020) reported that PBC has no effect on destination and revisit intention as a result of the research on the destination and revisit intention for street flavors in the context of the TPB. Therefore, the following hypothesis was developed to understand the perception of how much control they have in supporting green kitchen practices.

H3: Individuals' PBC to support green cuisine practices affects restaurant choice intention.

3. Method

The study evaluated the effectiveness of attitude towards behaviour (ATB), Subjective Norm (SN) and Perceived Behavioral Control (PBC) on individuals'

intention to choose a restaurant with Green Kitchen Practices. In this context, the model of the study is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Study model

A questionnaire was prepared for the study, and the data were obtained online via Google Forms. The ethics committee permission required to get the data in this study was obtained with the decision of Kastamonu University Social and Human Sciences Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Board dated 07.02.2024 and numbered 2/20. The study population consisted of individuals living in İstanbul, İzmir and Bursa. These three provinces are three of the four provinces with the highest population density in Türkiye. In addition, İstanbul is the province that hosts the most tourists in Türkiye. In addition, studies on green restaurants are concentrated in İstanbul (Keşkekçi & Gençer, 2023; Yazıcıoğlu & Aydın, 2018; Kurnaz & Özdoğan, 2018). These three provinces, which are geographically close to each other, constitute 40.5% of Türkiye's gross national product (tuik.gov.tr). In the study, convenience sampling, one of the non-probability-based sampling methods, was preferred. Convenience sampling is based on the principle that everyone who voluntarily responds to the questionnaire is included in the sample (Ural & Kılıç, 2005). In this context, the questionnaire prepared through Google Forms was applied to 428 volunteer participants.

The questions in the questionnaire were prepared in consultation with academicians who are food and beverage management experts. The scale used in the questionnaire is the Planned Behaviour Theory scale used in Kargiglioğlu's (2019) doctoral dissertation titled "The Effect of Street Flavours on Destination Choice and Revisit Intention in the Context of Planned Behaviour Theory: The Case of İstanbul Province", the TPB scale used in his doctoral thesis was applied to the study. The scale comprises four sub-dimensions: ATB, SN, PBC and BI.

The first part of the questionnaire consists of 17 statements and the second part consists of 6 statements, totalling 23. Participants evaluated the statements in the questionnaire form, including ATB, SN, PBC and BI, using a 5-point Likert scale. The second part of the questionnaire includes demographic questions regarding the participants' characteristics.

The data obtained were uploaded to an Excel spreadsheet via Google Forms and then coded and trans-

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ferred to the IBM SPSS Statistics 23 application. First, reliability analysis and results of the questions in the scale used in the research were obtained. Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of ATB, SN, PBC and BI were calculated separately. Accordingly, ATB 0.970, SN 0.939, BI 0.968, and PBC 0.877 were obtained. Since Cronbach's Alpha coefficients were more significant than 0.8, it was concluded that the data test was highly reliable (Nunnally, 1978; Anderson & Gerbing, 1988; Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson & Tatham, 1998).

To evaluate the suitability of the data collected within the scope of the research for factor analysis, KMO and Bartlett Sphericity Test were applied. Since the KMO value is above 0.60 (0.957), the data set is suitable for factor analysis (Table 1).

Table 1. KMO and Bartlett's Test Results

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy		10536.629
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	10536.629
	Df	136
	Sig.	.000

To determine the validity and reliability of the scale used in the research. The factor loadings and the explained variance of the statements on the scale are shown in Table 2, and it is determined that the scale is reliable and valid.

Table 2. Factor Loadings and Explain the Variance of the items in the scale

ATB	Dining in restaurants with green kitchen practices is extraordinary.	.795	Variance Explained 34.751 Reliability: .970
ATB	Dining in restaurants with green culinary practices is spectacular.	.736	
ATB	It is fun to eat restaurants with green kitchen practices.	.634	
ATB	It makes sense to eat in restaurants with green kitchen practices.	.813	
ATB	Dining in restaurants with green culinary practices is relaxing.	.801	
ATB	Eating in restaurants with green kitchen practices is essential.	.836	
ATB	It is helpful to eat in restaurants with green kitchen practices.	.867	
ATB	It is good to eat in restaurants with green culinary practices.	.847	
SN	Through its messaging, the media encourages me to eat in restaurants with green culinary practices.	.703	Variance Explained 31.521 Reliability: .939
SN	Most of the people who are dear to me expect me to eat in environmentally friendly restaurants	.855	
SN	Most people dear to me think I should prefer environmentally friendly restaurants.	.858	
SN	Most of the people who are dear to me prefer environmentally sustainable restaurants.	.851	
BI	I intend to prefer environmentally friendly restaurants for dining soon.	.645	Variance Explained 14.592 Reliability: .968
BI	I plan to go to environmentally friendly restaurants to eat.	.666	
BI	I prefer environmentally friendly restaurants, and I plan to make it happen.	.679	
PBC	If I want to choose environmentally friendly restaurants to eat in, nothing can stop me.	.675	Variance Explained 7.153 Reliability: .970
PBC	It is entirely up to me to choose environmentally sustainable restaurants.	.783	

ATB: Attitude Towards Behaviour SN: Subjective Norm PBC: Perceived Behavioural Control BI: Behavioural Intention

Findings

The demographic characteristics of the participants are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Demographic Findings

		N	Current %	Cumulative %			N	Current %	Cumulative %
Gender	Woman	258	60.3	60.3	Profession	Public Employee	162	37.9	37.9
	Man	170	39.7	100		Private Sector Employee	140	13.8	51.6
	Total	428	100			Tradesmen	5	1.2	52.8
M.Sta	Married	196	45.8	45.8		Retired	3	7	53.5
	Single	232	54.2	100		Housewife	40	9.3	62.9
	Total	428	100			Student	59	32.7	95.6
Age	18-25	173	40.4	40.4		Unemployed	9	2.1	97.7
	26-33	63	14.7	55.1		Other	10	2.3	100
	34-41	92	21.5	76.6		Total	428	100	
	42-49	65	15.2	91.8		Low Income	82	19.2	19.2
	50 and +	35	8.2	100	Lower Middle Income	95	22.2	41.4	
	Total	428	100		Middle Income	209	48.8	90.2	
School(Most recent)	Primary education	21	4.9	4.9	Middle Upper Income	38	8.9	99.1	
	High School	122	28.5	33.4	High Income	4	0.9	100	
	Associate Degree	59	13.8	47.2	Total	428	100		
	License	172	40.2	87.4					
	Postgraduate	54	12.6	100					
	Total	428	100						

The total number of participants in the survey was 428, and 428 of the individuals who participated in the survey answered the questions. 60.3% of the participants were women and 39.7% were men.

Table 4. Pearson Correlation Analysis

		Attitude Towards Behaviour	Subjective Norm	Perceived Behavioural Control	Behavioural Intention
Attitude Towards Behaviour	Pearson Correlation	1	.737**	.785**	.823**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	428	428	428	428

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Subjective Norm	Pearson Correlation	.737**	1	.703**	.859**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	428	428	428	428
Perceived Behavioural Control	Pearson Correlation	.785**	.703**	1	.835**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	428	428	428	428
Behavioural Intention	Pearson Correlation	.823**	.859**	.835**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	428	428	428	428

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

When The Pearson Correlation analysis is examined, it is seen that there are statistically significant and positive correlations between ATB, SN, PBC and BI, which are the sub-dimensions of the TPB. Hence;

1. There is a significant and positive relationship between ATB and SN ($r = 0.737$; $p < 0.01$)
2. There is a significant and positive relationship between ATB and PBC ($r = 0.785$; $p < 0.01$)
3. ATB and BI have a significant and positive relationship ($r = 0.823$; $p < 0.01$).
4. SN and PBC have a significant positive relationship ($r = 0.703$; $p < 0.01$).

5. SN and BI have a significant positive relationship ($r = 0.859$; $p < 0.01$).

6. PBC and BI have a significant positive relationship ($r = 0.835$; $p < 0.01$).

Testing Hypotheses

To investigate the effect of the sub-dimensions in the TPB scale on each other, linear regression analysis was conducted. Linear regression is an approach to modeling the relationship between the dependent variable (BI) and the independent variable or variables (Kılıç, 2013).

Table 5. H1: Individuals' attitudes towards GKP positively affect restaurant choice intention.

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.533	.109		4.879	.000
Attitude Towards Behavior	.864	.029	.823	29.870	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Behavioral Intention

As seen in Table 5, ATB has a significant and positive effect on consumer restaurant choice intention ($\beta = 0.823$; $t = 29.870$ $p < 0.05$). H1 is accepted.

Table 6. H2: Individuals' subjective norms about supporting green cuisine practices positively affect restaurant choice intention

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.733	.089		8.219	.000
Subjective Norm	.868	.025	.859	34.604	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Behavioural Intention

As seen in Table 6, subjective norms significantly and positively affect consumer restaurant choice intention ($\beta=0.859$; $t=34.604$ $p<0.05$). H2 is accepted.

Table 7. H3: Individuals' PBC over supporting green cuisine practices affects restaurant choice intention

Model	Unstandardised Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.586	.103		5.700	.000
Perceived Behavioral Control	.857	.027	.835	31.301	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Behavioral Intention

As seen in Table 7, PBC significantly and positively affects consumer restaurant choice intention ($\beta=0.835$; $t=31.301$ $p<0.05$). H3 is accepted.

Discussion, Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examines whether the variables in the sub-dimensions of the TPB affect restaurant choice intention. In order to understand the significance level of the effects of the independent variables (attitude towards behavior, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control) in the theory of planned behavior scale on the dependent variable, the consumer's restaurant choice intention, three hypotheses were made. These hypotheses were tested with the data collected through the questionnaire.

Theoretical implications

As a result of the statistical analysis, it was concluded that ATB, SN, and PBC are significant and positive in explaining consumers' intentions to choose a restaurant.

When the literature is examined, Dutta et al. (2008) investigated individuals' attitudes and behavioral intentions in their study on consumers' orientation towards restaurants with green practices. The result that environmentally friendly individuals prefer restaurants with green practices supports the hypothesis that the attitude towards behavior obtained in the current study positively affects the restaurant choice intention. The effect of consumers' ATB on behavioral intention Dewald et al. (2014), in their study in the USA, revealed that health-conscious consumers prefer restaurants with green practices where organic, local, and healthy beverages are served. In the literature, studies on the effects of ATB on behavioral intention have emphasized significant findings on consumer attitude, behavior, satisfaction, and willingness to pay and concluded that consumers have positive effects on their preference for restaurants with environmentally friendly practices

(Dutta et al., 2008; Eren et al., 2023; Schubert et al., 2010; Han & Kim, 2010). These findings support the present study.

When the results of the analysis related to SN are analyzed, it is found that the effect of SN on restaurant choice intention is upbeat. This shows that participants are influenced by the individual or group they refer to (family, spouse, friend, colleague, doctor or manager). In the literature, Han and Kim (2010) concurred with the findings of the study with the result that SN affects customers' intention to revisit a hotel with green practices, while Chou et al., 2012, in their research in Taiwan, reported that there was no social pressure, which does not support the current study.

When the analysis results related to PBC are examined, it is found that the effect of PBC on restaurant choice intention is optimistic. Perceived behavioural control, a vital part of the TPB, shows that the extent to which respondents perceive that they are in control when choosing a restaurant impacts their intention to choose restaurants with environmentally friendly green practices. Looking at the literature, Chou et al. (2012), in a study combining the TPB and the theory of innovation adoption, found that the positive effects of PBC on the adoption of green practices support the current research. Kargiglioğlu's (2020) study on destination and revisit intention for street flavors in the context of the TPB shows that PBC does not affect destination and revisit intention, which does not overlap with the findings of this study. When the current research results are considered, it is seen that ATB, SN, and PBC have positive effects on behavioral intention.

Managerial implications

Considering the findings of this study, it is clear that consumer intention to prefer restaurants with environmentally friendly green practices is positive. Restaurant owners need to communicate with their customers about GKP and make them more aware that they are buying a green restaurant. This is be-

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cause many customers need more knowledge about the benefits of green kitchen practices, especially on environmental issues.

Within the scope of developing projects for the benefit of society, which is one of the essential duties of academicians, the process of green restaurants, from procurement to production and serving customers, can be designed as educational projects. However, researchers can develop a theory of preference for green restaurants.

While sustainable development continues to maintain its importance as an essential concept for the whole world, GKP can be considered a critical application on the road to the success that public authorities aim to achieve by 2030. In this regard, the relevant public administrations can be encouraged with a study similar to the Green Star for hotels regarding certification. Although this issue is being addressed as a civil society movement through associations, its realization under the coordination of the relevant ministries will contribute to environmental awareness in society.

Limitations and Future Research

As with every research study, this study also has limitations. The study was conducted with participants living in Istanbul, Izmir and Bursa. In addition, the convenience sampling method was used in sample selection. At the same time, this study is based on the TPB to explain green restaurant choice intention. Future studies can be conducted using different theories and differentiating the sampling method. Studies have focused on independent restaurants rather than hotels with green kitchen applications. Studies that reveal the consumer's choice among different concepts within the hotel can be considered within the scope of expectation theory. This situation can help reveal consumers' decision-making processes for choosing green restaurants. Future research can develop the working model presented in this study with different variables.

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